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European AI Alliance

Launch of the AI Media Observatory by the AI4Media project

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AI4Media Project

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In October 2023, the [AI4Media project](#) launched its new AI Media Observatory, which is a knowledge platform that monitors and curates relevant research on AI in media and provides an overview of relevant experts in the field.

The Observatory aims to provide a one-stop-shop for the various stakeholder groups working in the intersection of AI and media and support the responsible use and development of AI technologies for the media sector.

The [AI Media Observatory](#) is the culmination of three years of work in the AI4Media consortium and was initially launched in a 'beta-version' earlier this year in April. Now the Observatory has been officially launched and has already built a repository of both written and audiovisual content that inspires and provides insights into good practices and cutting-edge knowledge on the usage of AI in the media. Furthermore, it now features 18 experts on social, technical, and legal issues in its

expert directory, which is aimed at facilitating dialogue with stakeholders.

The overarching goal of the Observatory is to support the ongoing efforts of the multidisciplinary community of professionals who are working towards ensuring the responsible use of AI in the media sector. Drawing on the expert knowledge and expertise of more than 30 leading research and industry partners in the field of media and AI, it aims to contribute to the broader discussion and understanding of the development and use of AI in the sector and its impacts on society, the economy, and people.

The Observatory aims to fulfill this goal by curating relevant content that provides expert perspectives on the potentials and challenges that AI poses for the media sector through its sections '[Your AI Media Feed](#)' for written content and '[Let's Talk AI and Media](#)' for audiovisual content. It also provides an easy overview of relevant experts in the field through the '[Find your AI Media Expert](#)' directory.

You can find more information about the Observatory in this [brochure](#).

How can you contribute with relevant content?

The AI Media Observatory publishes content that focuses on the impact of AI in the media sector. This could include but is not limited to, impacts of legislation changes, economic impacts in the sector (e.g., layoffs or investments), societal impacts (e.g., potentials of AI in battling misinformation) or social and ethical approaches to AI.

The content featured on the Observatory is curated by an editorial board that convenes on a monthly basis to evaluate the content that is suggested, either by partners in the AI4Media consortium or by the public. The content is evaluated on the basis of the editorial principles. The composition of the editorial board and the editorial principles are available here can be found [here](#).

We welcome all stakeholders to contribute content to the new observatory by utilising this online submission [form](#).

Sign up to be featured in the expert directory!

The [expert directory](#), which is one of the new features of the Observatory, provides an overview of relevant experts across the varying subdisciplines that engage in AI and Media and aims to support civil society and media professionals who are seeking knowledge on a specific topic on AI in media.

Via the directory you can easily search, find, and contact a relevant expert within the field of media and AI - whether it be a technical, legal, or social expert. The expert directory is not limited to AI4Media partners; rather it is open for all relevant experts to sign up to create a wide network of experts.

To be featured in the directory, the experts must hold expertise that is directly relevant for AI in the media sector. Experts applying to be included in the directory will undergo an eligibility check by the editorial board of the Observatory.

We invite experts from Europe and beyond to fill out the [application](#) to be featured in the expert directory!

About AI4Media

Funded under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, the project aspires to become a Centre of Excellence engaging a wide network of researchers across Europe and beyond, focusing on delivering the next generation of core AI advances and training to serve the Media sector, while ensuring that the European values of ethical and trustworthy AI are embedded in future AI deployments.

Download the project brochure [here](#)!

This blogpost was authored by [Anna Schjøtt Hansen](#), a PhD Candidate at the Media Studies Department of the

University of Amsterdam. Anna's research focuses on the on-the-ground political dynamics that emerge from how AI is represented, developed and used in the media sector.

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AI Media Observatory

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